

AVIATION TERMINOLOGY OF THE ENGLISH IN THE ASPECT OF TRANSLATION INTO UZBEK AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *In this article, problems of aviation terminology of the English in the aspect of translation them into Uzbek and Russian languages are raised. According to the author translation is an active participant in the modern process and it is impossible to imagine the modern world without it. As the author regards the problem of translating aviation terms from English into Uzbek and Russian is more relevant than ever, because this layer of vocabulary is an integral part of scientific and technical industries. The author indicates the key problems in this sphere.*

Key words: *abbreviation, aspect, aviation, definition, English, equivalent, explanation, language, term, terminology, translation*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilining aviatsiya terminologiyasining ularni o'zbek va rus tillariga tarjima qilish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Muallifning fikricha, tarjima zamonaviy jarayonning faol ishtirokchisi bo'lib, zamonaviy dunyoni usiz tasavvur etib bo'lmaydi. Muallif aviatsiya atamalarini ingliz tilidan o'zbek va rus tillariga tarjima qilish muammosini har qachongidan ham dolzarb deb hisoblar ekan, chunki lug'atning bu qatlami fan-texnika tarmoqlarining ajralmas qismi hisoblanadi. Muallif ushbu sohadagi asosiy muammolarni ko'rsatadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *qisqartma, aspekt, aviatsiya, ta'rif, inglizcha, ekvivalent, tushuntirish, til, atama, terminologiya, tarjima*

Аннотация. *В данной статье поднимаются проблемы авиационной терминологии английского языка в аспекте перевода их на узбекский и русский языки. По мнению автора, перевод является активным участником современного процесса и без него невозможно представить современный мир. По мнению автора, проблема перевода авиационных терминов с английского языка на узбекский и русский языки актуальна как никогда, поскольку этот пласт лексики является неотъемлемой частью научно-технической отрасли. Автор указывает ключевые проблемы в этой сфере.*

Ключевые слова: *аббревиатура, аспект, авиация, определение, английский язык, эквивалент, объяснение, язык, термин, терминология, перевод.*

Translation plays a huge role in the development of aviation. As A.V.Fedorov states, “we are far from absolutizing the role and significance of translation. Undoubtedly, translation is an active participant in the modern process and it is impossible to imagine the modern world without it. Translation can and should be a carrier, conductor and discoverer of everything most valuable for all peoples” [4, p. 18]. Speaking about translation as a product of translation activity, the most general and capacious, but at the same time brief definition of translation can be the formulation “translation is an analogue of the original”. In the case where we try to define translation as a process, a type of activity, it should be said that the translation process can be understood as a special oral or written activity, the purpose of which is to recreate the text

existing in the original language into the target language while preserving the content and quality of the original. In the theory and practice of translation, the term "translation transformation" also functions, which means the transformation of the original text. In order to preserve the individuality inherent in each text and to obtain the most complete translation equivalent, such transformations are necessary and mandatory. Just as there is no single concept of "translation" and "translation transformation" in linguistics, there is no single classification of translation transformations.

Each linguist offers his own types and methods of their grouping, but the most common is the classification of translation transformations proposed by V.N. Komissarov, according to which the following are distinguished: 1. Lexical transformations - describe the formal and substantive relations between words and phrases in the original and translation, these include: translation transcription; transliteration; calculus; lexical semantic substitutions (specification, generalization, modulation). 2. Grammatical transformations - this is a change in the structure of a sentence, as well as all kinds of substitutions of a syntactic and morphological order. Types of grammatical transformations: literal translation (syntactic assimilation); division of sentences; combination of sentences; substitutions (word forms, parts of speech, members or types of sentences). 3. Lexico-grammatical (complex) transformations are the translation of lexical units of the original by using in the translation units of the target language, the meanings of which do not correspond to the meanings of the original units, but which can be obtained by logical transformations. Such transformations include: antonymic translation; descriptive translation (explication); compensation. 4. Technical methods of translation are transformations that violate the formal similarity of the translation with the original, but ensure a higher level of equivalence. Thus, in modern aviation terminology, two main types of abbreviations can be distinguished: 1. Abbreviations of the initial type, when commonly used vocabulary is combined with a narrow professional or scientific term. This includes the main names of parts, devices and materials. This group is subdivided into: 1. Abbreviations formed from the initial letters of words, for example, AEA (Association of European Airlines); abbreviations formed from combinations of the initial sounds of words, for example, nav aids (navigation aids). 2. Abbreviations of the "syllabic" type, i.e. formed from the first syllables of a word, for example, DME (distance measuring equipment) [1, p. 90-91]. It should be noted that the lexical-semantic term formation brought lexical units with new meanings into aviation terminology, for example, jacket, jar, to load. The lexical-synthetic method also forms many terminological combinations, for example, radio communication equipment, snow clearing equipment, etc.

English aviation terminology was supplemented by the morphological method due to: - suffixation, for example, bear-ing, circle-ing, control(l)-er, safety; word composition, for example, accident-free, aircraft, autothrottle, gyroplane. Another feature of English aviation terminology is the use of prepositions in term formation, for example, leveling-off, circle-to-land, lock-on, noising-over, take-off, etc. Translation of technical texts is one of the most difficult types of translation due to the presence of a significant number of terms characteristic of a particular area of knowledge and a specific style of presenting the material. There are several points of view regarding the essence of the concept of a term. For example, A.A.Reformatsky believed that terms are special words that strive to be an unambiguous, precise expression of concepts and names of things [1, p. 61]. According to O. S. Akhmanova, a term is a word or phrase of a special, scientific or technical language, necessary for the precise expression of special concepts and the designation of special objects [2, p. 474]. S.D.Shelov, discussing terms, listed their five main characteristics: semantic precision, unambiguity of the term, stylistic

neutrality, nominativeness of the term and its systematicity [3, p. 5]. Taking into account these properties of terms, we can conclude that their translation requires a special approach and preparation. A terminological unit must be given a scientific and technical equivalent in the target language, which is only possible if the translator has achieved a full understanding of the context. This is due to the fact that many English terms have too wide a range of meanings. For example, the English term *bottle* has the following equivalents in Uzbek: 'bottle', 'body', 'cylinder', and also 'rocket accelerator'. And, for example, the term *cell* corresponds to the following Uzbek lexical units: 'cell', 'galvanic element', 'date'. Let us consider five main methods of translating English aviation terminology into Uzbek using examples: equivalent selection, tracing, transcription, transliteration, and descriptive translation. Equivalent selection requires the presence of a lexical unit in the target language that is absolutely analogous to a word or phrase in the original language. When using this method, the translator's responsibility is to find the equivalent in the target language and compare it with the original term. For example, when translating the terms *loadmaster* – 'loading and unloading equipment operator' [4, p. 196], *luggage area* – 'baggage compartment', *mid-range airlift* – 'medium-range airlift', equivalent selection is used, that is, a stable unit with a certain semantic load. Tracing is a translation transformation in which the elements of a word are replaced by lexical analogues in the target language, that is, a literal translation of morphemes occurs. The Comprehensive English-Russian and Russian-English Aviation Dictionary contains terminological units translated using this method: *dual control* [4, p. 143], *closed-loop analysis* [4, p. 95], *carrier-based* [4, p. 85]. Transliteration is a translation method that involves letter-by-letter recreation of a lexical unit of one language by means of another. Examples from the aviation dictionary: *autopilot* [4, p. 56], *lift* [4, p. 191], *laser* [4, p. 186]. These terms are translated into Russian/Uzbek using transliteration. The essence of transcription, in turn, consists in reproducing the sound form of a word by means of the translation language. For example, *baggage* [4, p. 60], *base* [4, p. 60], *liner* [4, p. 194] were translated. Descriptive translation implies an explanation of the term. It is used if the word or phrase has no equivalent recorded in dictionaries. This technique is used to translate terms such as, for example, *lineup* [4, p. 194], *maintenance cycle* [4, p. 201], *mast-mounted assembly* [4, p. 203]. Thus, due to the lack of a shorter equivalent in the target language, these terms were translated descriptively. The aviation industry is rapidly developing and is replete with terminological vocabulary. The problem of translating aviation terms from English into Uzbek is more relevant than ever, because this layer of vocabulary is an integral part of scientific and technical industries. In this area, a translator is required to have specialized knowledge, professional vocabulary, as well as the main methods of translation transformations to correctly convey the meaning of terms.

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